

Original Research Article

Climate Pattern and Recurrent Drought of Mieso Area, West Hararghe, Ethiopia

Gelana Amente* and Berhanu Mengistu

Abstract

Haramaya University, College of Natural and Computational Sciences, P.O. Box 138, Dire Dawa, Ethiopia

*Corresponding Author's E-mail:
amentegelana@gmail.com

Drought can generally be defined as the persistence of precipitation deficit. It can range from mild to extreme depending on the severity of the lack of precipitation. The area around Mieso during the times of benign years is known and praised for its abundant sorghum production. But over last couple of decades, it is persistently affected by drought and consistently demanding grain charity. This study attempts to investigate the cyclic pattern and severity of the drought and its link to the atmospheric teleconnections. For this study, data from three closest meteorological stations (Mieso, Chiro and Hirna) were obtained and analyzed. Out of the three stations Chiro station data were found to be slightly similar to Mieso data. For the data analysis Mieso data was used with missing years data filled in from the analyzed Chiro rainfall data. The analyses were made using Dekadal Dryness Indicator (DDI), Start of Season (SoS), Runs theory, the Standard Precipitation Index (SPI) and the Standard Precipitation and Evapotranspiration Index (SPEI). The rainy seasons selected for the analysis were Feb.-May (the short rainy season) and June – Sept. (the main rainy season) separately and by combining the two seasons. Besides, the drought years were related to global atmospheric and oceanic teleconnections. The averaged rainfall results revealed the 2nd dekad of March and the first dekad of July as start of season (SoS) for the two rainy seasons, respectively. The 1ecadal results showed the lengths of the two rainy seasons to be three months or less. The run theory exhibited drought intensities of -89 mm, -117 mm and -108 mm during the years 1991-93, 2002-2003 and 2008/2009, respectively. Based on SPI analysis, the seasons (MAM and JAS) each had one extreme and one severe drought years. MAM rainy season experienced two while the JAS rainy season had four moderate drought years. The combined six months rainy season experienced 2 severe and six moderate drought years. SPEI showed identical drought years (2002 extremely severe and 2008 severe) with SPI. The severe droughts of the two seasons seem to have 10 year cycles and the moderate dry years came six years after the severe drought years. Nearly 50% of the time there were start of season failures, which partly contributed to the drought. The droughts were generally stronger during El Nino years dominated by El Nino dominance period and when ENSO was positive. Since it is roughly possible to predict these events, it is possible to roughly predict the drought years but it may still be difficult to predict the intensities.

Keywords: Dekadal dryness indicator, Mieso, Runs theory, SPI, SPEI, Start of season.

INTRODUCTION

Crops are primarily affected by drought. In areas where there is rainfall deficit and the rate of evapotranspiration is relatively high, only crops that are very tolerant to

drought can endure the climate (Rojas *et al.*, 2014). For Farmers making their livelihood on such areas life is precarious and very challenging, especially during times

of drought.

Drought over a specific region can generally be defined as the rainfall deficit over extended time. It is bound by space and time meaning the location is specified and the time of occurrence and the duration must also be specific. Drought may be conceptually or operationally defined.

The operational definitions of drought are: agricultural, meteorological, hydrological and socioeconomic droughts. They objectively define criteria, the start and end and severity of drought (Zargar *et al.*, 2011). Meteorological drought is caused by lower than normal precipitation for a prolonged time. Means of measurement for such types of droughts are meteorological parameters such as rainfall, temperatures, relative humidity, sunshine hours, etc. Meteorological drought has some implication on agricultural drought and can also be the cause of agricultural drought. In this study focus is made on meteorological drought.

Agricultural drought is caused when plant available water falls below the required limit usually during a critical crop growth stage. Hydrologic drought is caused when one or a combination of factors such as stream flow, soil moisture or groundwater is/are not available. Socioeconomic drought is caused when a loss occurs in expected return, usually measured by social and economic indicators (Senay *et al.*, 2015). Precipitation deficiency instigates meteorological drought and it in turn impacts soil moisture content (i.e., causes agricultural drought). Low recharge from the soil to water features such as streams and lakes causes a delayed hydrological drought.

Besides the type, droughts are fundamentally characterized by their severity, duration and spatial distributions. Frequency, magnitude (cumulated deficit), predictability, rate of onset and timing are also additional characteristics. Duration can vary from weeks up to a few years. Because of drought's dynamic nature, a region can experience wet and dry spells simultaneously when considering various timescales. The accumulated deficit of water (e.g., precipitation, soil moisture or runoff) below some threshold occurs during a drought period (Zargar *et al.*, 2011). Severity can be seen in two forms: the degree of the precipitation deficit (i.e., magnitude) or the degree of impacts resulting from the deficit (Wu *et al.*, 2007). The other important issue is the frequency or the return period of the drought. It is defined as the average time between drought events that have a severity that is equal to or greater than a threshold (Zargar *et al.*, 2011).

Drought is identified by over 91 drought impacts analyses (Senay *et al.*, 2015) and drought indices. The drought indices make use of things like vegetation health, alone or water resources and evapotranspiration combined. Indicators can be meteorological, hydrological or water supply-and-demand. Meteorological indicators include precipitation, potential evapotranspiration and cloud cover, while hydrological indicators include stream

flow and groundwater level. Water supply-and-demand indicators include reservoir storage. The use of some indicators such as precipitation, potential evapotranspiration and soil- and vegetation-cover characteristics has wider applications and influence ((Zargar *et al.*, 2011).

Large-scale and regional/local forcings produce a region's climate. The forcings are produced by an interaction that operate from the global scales of the general circulation of the atmosphere and oceans, through the regional-scale of tropical cyclones, to the more local scale of the effects of coasts, mountains, and land use. The dominant influences of an area are the coupled ocean-atmosphere phenomena such as El Niño-Southern Oscillation (ENSO) and the Indian Ocean Dipole (IOD). ENSO is by far the most energetic of these. El Niño is a local warming of surface waters or Sea Surface Temperature (SST) that takes place in the entire equatorial zone of the central and eastern Pacific Ocean and it affects the atmospheric circulation worldwide (Rojas *et al.*, 2014; Stuecker, *et al.*, 2017).

An El Niño episode is associated with persistent warmer than average sea surface temperatures and consistent changes in wind and rainfall patterns. The Southern Oscillation is an East-West balancing movement of air masses between the Pacific and the Indo-Australian areas (Rojas *et al.*, 2014). It is associated (roughly synchronized) with typical wind patterns and El Niño and is measured by the Southern Oscillation Index (SOI). El Niño is the oceanic component, while the Southern Oscillation is the atmospheric one. This combination gives rise to the term ENSO (El Niño – Southern Oscillation). Although there is no perfect correlation between El Niño and the Southern Oscillations as regards minor variations, large negative values of the SOI are associated with warm events (Rojas *et al.*, 2014).

ENSO accounts for more than 20-30% global climate variability among the global climate drivers, (Anderson and Strahler, 2008). It is considered as one of the key climate drivers for predicting climate variability over different parts of world. El Niño refers to warming of the central and eastern Pacific or the entire Pacific basin and it affects trade winds, which in turn affect the atmosphere and weather patterns. The duration of El Niño lasts from 5-19 months.

A somewhat similar mode of SSTA variability to ENSO with both a weaker amplitude and smaller spatial scale exists in the Indian Ocean and is termed as Indian Ocean Dipole (IOD) (Stuecker *et al.*, 2017). The Indian Ocean Dipole (IOD) is the Indian Ocean counterpart of the Pacific El Niño and La Niña events. The term dipole means two “poles” or two areas of differences in SSTs between the Arabian Sea (western pole) located north of the equator and the eastern Indian Ocean (eastern pole) located south of the equator. Both of these poles are situated within the equatorial belt of the Indian Ocean

Table 1. Geographical locations of the study area and the surrounding meteorological stations.

Meteorological station	Longitude	Latitude	Average altitude (m)	Distance from the Mieso (km)
Chiro	40.8715 E	9.0725 N	1792	30
Hirna	41.1 E	9.216667 N	1822	70
Mieso	40.75 E	9.23333 N	1332 (900 – 1600)	

Figure 1. Map of the study district in Oromiya region (Source: Hussen, 2007)

(i.e., between 10°N and 10°S). They have a northwest-southeast diagonal orientation because of the physical configuration of the North Indian Ocean. Positive IODs are often associated with El Niño and negative IODs with La Niña. The dipole in sea surface temperature (SST) anomalies is accompanied by abundant rainfall over the western Indian Ocean–East Africa and scarce rainfall over eastern Indian Ocean–Indonesia. IOD influences the rainfall of the Indian summer monsoon of the East Africa short rainy seasons (Manatsa and Behera, 2013). Only small fractions (32%) of IOD events occur independently of ENSO events (Stuecker *et al.*, 2017). Furthermore, there is a close relationship between ENSO and IOD variability.

The purpose of this study is to investigate the persistent drought that affects Mieso district. This district is one of the major sorghum producing areas of west Hararghe but it is almost always prone to drought that affects both crop and livestock production (Kahsay, 2006). The drought also forces the people of the area to find alternative means of subsistence among which charcoal production and sale is the major one. This in turn devastates the dwindling tree populations that are grown in the area. The removal of trees is gradually converting the semi-aridity to more aridity, which makes the problem even worse. In order to help the farmers and

to devise adaptation strategy it is necessary to know the drought cycle and the drought intensity of the area. Hence the study mainly focuses on frequency of drought and the cycles of severe and the extreme droughts. The study also tries to link the droughts to global atmospheric and oceanic phenomena.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Description of the Study Area

The study focused on Mieso district of Oromiya region, which includes Asebot; an area that is well known for its sorghum production. Mieso is located 288 km east of Addis Ababa, Capital city of Ethiopia. The total land area of the district is 196,026 ha (Hussen, 2007). The geographical locations of the study area and the surrounding meteorological stations are given in Table 1. Figure 1

The mean annual temperature of the area varies between 24°C and 28°C. There are different types of soils but the dominant types are vertisols (Hussen, 2007). Agro-ecologically the district is classified as lowland (locally known as Kola) with mean annual rainfall ranging from 400 to 900 mm.

Table 2. List of rainfall-based drought indicators

Drought Index/ Indicator	Method	Resolution/ Scale	Drought Indicator		
			Short-term	Seasonal	Annual
Standardized precipitation index (SPI)	Rainfall-based	10 km	Y	Y	Y
Start of season (SOS)	Rainfall-based	10 km		Y	
Rainfall anomaly	Rainfall-based	10 km	Y		
Dryness indicators	Rainfall based	10 km	Y		

(Partially extracted from Senay *et al.*, 2015)

Data Sources

In this study two data sources were used. The first is the meteorological data of 31 years for Chiro and Hirna stations (1986 and 2016) and 23years for Mieso station (1991 – 2013) obtained from the Ethiopian Meteorological Agency. The second is the drought history obtained from the Disaster Management office of West Hararghe zone (located in Chiro).

Method of Data Analysis

Since Mieso does not have complete data of thirty years, the first task was to assess the similarities/differences of the three meteorological stations and out of the two to select the one that closely resembles Mieso data. This was required to fill the data of the missing years of Mieso station. The meteorological data of the three stations were analyzed for rainfall by calculating 30-year averages for Chiro and Hirna, and 23 –year average for Mieso. The data were plotted to find rainfall patterns over the study years and also to compare the patterns of the three areas. Thereafter, the Chiro rainfall data was extrapolated to fill in the missing data of Mieso for the years 1986 to 1990 and 2014 to 2016.

The main focus was made on the bimodal rainfall, which generally take place during the two rainfall seasons, namely, in Spring (Feb. – May) and in Summer (June – Sept.). For the analysis, first the thirty year averages were calculated to find the rainfall pattern of the area after which individual year rainfalls were compared with the study time averages. Analyses were made for the two seasons individually and then by combining the two seasons.

In order to study drought, five drought indicators were used. Those were, dekadal average rainfalls, start of season (SoS), runs theory, standard precipitation index (SPI) and the standard precipitation and evapotranspiration index (SPEI). In each assessment, each year rainfall was compared with the 30 year averages. The dekads were used to know the lengths of the seasons. The SoS was used to determine the planting times during each season and also to know the anomalies in SoS. The runs theory was used to know the

times of rainfall deficit, duration and intensity. The SPI and SPEI were used as the standard drought indices.

The appropriateness of the two drought indicators (SPI and SOS) were assessed using the information given in Table 2 (Senay *et al.*, 2015). Rainfall-based drought indicators offer direct and simple methods to monitor onset, expansion and intensity of drought situations (Senay *et al.*, 2015). From among the many drought indicators Table 2 shows the ones that are mostly rainfall-based.

Monthly dryness indicators are short-term drought indicators. They are known by counting the numbers of rainy and non-rainy days. A rainy day is any day with greater than 1 mm of rainfall. The analysis is made by analyzing rainfall occurrence over the previous 30 days from the current date (Senay *et al.*, 2015). Generally, the higher the number of rainy days, the lower the dryness. But this method does not help to quantify the amount of rainfall. On the other hand, the higher the numbers of consecutive dry days, the higher the dryness intensity.

Dekadal Dryness Indicator

Dekadal measurement of rainfall is important to know the amount of rainfall obtained within 10 days (a dekad). For this purpose each rainy month was divided into three dekads. The pattern or the distribution of rainfall obtained during the rainy season could then be obtained by bar-plotting the rainfalls for the entire dekads of the season. Such plots were good to know the start of season and also the end of season. The area investigated under this study has bimodal rainfall, the first from February to May and the second from June to September. The two seasons were first independently investigated and then combined together to know the total rainfall obtained during the two seasons.

Dekadal dryness indicator is a short-term drought indicator. Analysis of dekadal rainfall accumulations and comparing them with the long-term average rainfall for the same period provides useful information on the short-term dryness (Senay *et al.*, 2015). Continuous monitoring of time series information on dekadal rainfall accumulations and anomalies would further provide information on onset and progression of drought/dryness

Figure 2. Characteristics of local drought events with the theory of runs (Paulo and Pereira, 2006)

conditions. Furthermore, such information could be combined with other indicators such as evapotranspiration estimates (Senay *et al.*, 2015).

Dekadal rainfall is also important to know the percent of normal rainfall. The percent of normal precipitation is a meteorological drought index that describes the drought as the precipitation deviation from the normal (average). The normal usually corresponds to the mean of the past 30 years. Percent of normal is calculated by dividing a given precipitation by the normal (i.e., normalization of the rainfall). If such calculation is done for dekadal values it shows which dekads fall short of meeting the normal. In this study, the dekadal values were compared with the long time averages and those that fell more than 10% below the long-term averages were used to mark drought years.

Start of Season

Start of season (SoS) is an indicator of seasonal drought. Dividing seasonal rainfall into dekads is important to know the start of season and also the dekad/s during which precipitation is lower than what the specific crop grown in the area requires. In regions where agricultural practices are strongly tied to the arrival of the seasonal rains, SoS indicates the beginning of the wet season. The SoS is established when a sum total of at least 25 mm of rainfall has occurred in a given dekad (10-day period) and followed by a total of at least 20 mm of rainfall during the following two consecutive dekads (Senay *et al.*, 2015). The SoS anomaly is produced as deviation of SoS from the average of the last 10 years (in our case 23 years). Although the early arrival of SoS is not considered a hazard, the late arrival of SoS by 3 dekads or more signals a concern, especially in regions where the rainy season is short, i.e., less than 90 days (Senay *et al.*, 2015).

Analysis of Drought Characteristics by the Theory of Runs

A run is defined as a portion of the time series of a drought variable in which all values are either below or above the selected truncation level. In runs theory, drought intensity is the average value of a drought parameter below the threshold level and the theory of runs is based on the choice of the critical threshold level, y_c . The threshold y_c is obtained from the mean (μ) and the standard deviation (σ) of the long-time average rainfall (Paulo and Pereira, 2006) as:

$$y_c = \bar{\mu} - \bar{\sigma} \quad (2.1)$$

Considering a discrete time series such as years; $x_1, x_2, \dots, x_i, \dots, x_n$, the difference between y_c and x_i indicates a deficit or a surplus. A negative run, which indicates drought occurs when x_i is less than y_c . A run can be characterized by its length (L), its cumulated deficit (D) and its intensity (I), as described in Figure 2.

Any drought can be characterized by its duration, $L(s)$, which is the number of years the rainfall fell below the threshold, the cumulated deficit, $D(s)$, which is the sum of consecutive deficits and the intensity, $I(s)$, given by the ratio, $D(s)/L(s)$. In this study, each D_i was directly read from the bar graph plotted based on runs theory, $D(s)$ was summed for all the consecutive D_i s and $L(s)$ were obtained by counting the consecutive years of drought.

Standardized Precipitation Index (SPI)

SPI is meteorological drought index and it is solely based on precipitation data. SPI compares precipitation with its multiyear average. SPI overcomes the discrepancies resulting from using a non-standardized distribution by transforming the distribution of the precipitation record to a normal distribution. In this study, first, the precipitation record was fitted to one of the appropriate distributions

Table 3. Categories of SPI values

SPI value	Level of wetness or dryness
2.0+	extremely wet
1.5 to 1.99	very wet
1.0 to 1.49	moderately wet
-.99 to .99	near normal
-1.0 to -1.49	moderately dry
-1.5 to -1.99	severely dry
-2 and less	extremely dry

(Source: WMO, 2012)

that best fits the rainfall data. In our case, we fitted the data points to loglogistic distribution using Matlab software. After finding the two (scale, α and the shape, β) parameters of loglogistic distribution, we computed the cumulative probability function (cdf) using the two parameters again using Matlab software. The cdf is capable of properly describing the long-term observed rainfall series. Normally, in the absence of zero precipitation value, the cdf is the same as $H(P)$ (used to find the SPI), which is true in our case.

The next step of the SPI calculation was to apply an equi-probability transformation to the $[H(P)]$ values (Kumar *et al.*, undated) by finding t first

$$t = \sqrt{\ln\left(\frac{1}{(H(P))^2}\right)}; \quad \text{for } 0 < H(P) \leq 0.5 \quad (2.2a)$$

$$t = \sqrt{\ln\left(\frac{1}{(1-H(P))^2}\right)}; \quad \text{for } 0.5 < H(P) < 1 \quad (2.2b)$$

Thereafter the SPI values were calculated as:

$$SPI = -\left(t - \frac{c_0 + c_1t + c_2t^2}{1 + d_1t + d_2t^2 + d_3t^3}\right); \quad \text{for } 0 < H(P) \leq 0.5 \quad (2.3a)$$

$$SPI = \left(t - \frac{c_0 + c_1t + c_2t^2}{1 + d_1t + d_2t^2 + d_3t^3}\right); \quad \text{for } 0.5 < H(P) < 1 \quad (2.3b)$$

The constants are $c_0 = 2.515517$, $c_1 = 0.802853$, $c_2 = 0.010328$, $d_1 = 1.432788$, $d_2 = 0.189269$ and $d_3 = 0.001308$. In our study, Eq. 2.2 and 2.3 were evaluated using Microsoft Office Excel. Finally, bar graphs of the SPI values were drawn using Matlab and analyzed according to WMO (2012) SPI categories (Table 2).

The analyses were done for March to May (3-month), July to September (3-month) and combinations of the two (6-month) rainy seasons. The missing rainfall data (1986-1990 and 2014-2016) required for SPI calculation were

filled in by computing the missing Mieso data from Chiro's data.

The standardized precipitation and evapotranspiration index (SPEI)

The SPEI can account for the possible effects of temperature variability and temperature extremes unlike the SPI. When evapotranspiration cannot be evaluated, the use of SPI is preferable for the identification, analysis and monitoring of droughts in any climate region of the world (Bae *et al.*, 2018).

The SPEI can apply to different time scales, such as 1-, 3-, 6-, and 12-month scales, and therefore, it is capable of analyzing both short-term and long-term droughts (Bae *et al.*, 2018). Its computation requires complete precipitation and evapotranspiration (ET) for the same time and location. Even if the FAO Penman–Monteith (FAO-PM) is the recommended ET calculation method, when data required for the calculation of FAO-PM ET is not complete, other simpler but less accurate ET calculation methods can be used (Bae *et al.*, 2018). In our case, this was the problem and therefore we used the maximum temperature–based calculation of ET with the parameters optimized using one month data that satisfies FAO-PM ET. The optimized equation used was

$$ET = \frac{T_{mx}^{2.2}}{20.23 T_{mx} - 172.2} \quad (2.4)$$

With the value for ET_i and P_i , the difference between them for the month i was calculated as:

$$D_i = P_i - ET_i \quad (2.5)$$

Equation (2.5) provides a simple measure of the water surplus ($D_i > 0$) or deficit ($D_i < 0$) for the month i . The calculated D_i values were aggregated at different time scales (e.g., 3-month time scale and 6-month time scales).

$$D_n^k = \sum_{i=0}^{k-1} (P_{en-1} - ET_{cn-1}); \quad n \geq k \quad (2.6)$$

The k is the time scale and n is the analyzed month. In this study, the D_i values were fitted with loglogistic distribution to find the parameters after which the cumulative

Table 4. Classification of Standardized Precipitation Evapotranspiration Index (SPEI)

SPEI Value	Class
More than 2.00	Extremely wet (humid)
1.50–1.99	Severely wet
1.00–1.49	Moderately wet
0.50–0.99	Slightly wet
-0.49–0.49	Near normal
-0.99–0.50	Mild dry
-1.49– -1.00	Moderately dry
-1.99– -1.50	Severely dry
Less than -2.00	Extremely dry (drought)

(Source: Bae *et al.*, 2018)**Figure 3.** Study-years-averaged annual rainfalls of the three meteorological stations

distribution function (cdf = P) were evaluated using Matlab. The W s from which the SPEIs were evaluated were obtained as follows (Bae *et al.*, 2018).

$$W = \sqrt{-2 \ln(P)} \text{ for } P \leq 0.5 \text{ and } \quad (2.7a)$$

$$SPEI = W - \frac{c_0 + c_1 W + c_2 W^2}{1 - d_1 W + d_2 W^2 + d_3 W^3} \quad (2.8a)$$

$$\text{Else } W = \sqrt{-2 \ln(1 - P)} \quad (2.7b)$$

$$SPEI = \frac{c_0 + c_1 W + c_2 W^2}{1 - d_1 W + d_2 W^2 + d_3 W^3} - W \quad (2.8b)$$

The constants are $c_0 = 2.515517$, $c_1 = 0.802853$, $c_2 = 0.010328$, $d_1 = 1.432788$, $d_2 = 0.189269$, and $d_3 = 0.001308$. The thresholds of the SPEI for drought severity classes were analyzed based on the values given in Table 4 (Bae *et al.*, 2018).

Relating the droughts years to ENSO and IOD

The final analysis was made to link the droughts to

coupled atmospheric-oceanic phenomena such as El Niño Southern Oscillations (ENSO) and the Indian Ocean Dipole (IOD).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Most of the analyses of drought indicators require long-time-averaged data (≥ 30 years). The meteorological station of the study area had only 23 years rainfall data and hence it was necessary to look at other stations that are relatively close to the study area. The two additional stations selected were Chiro (Asebe Teferi) at a distance of 30 km and Hirna at a distance of 70 km. The rainfall patterns of the three areas are shown in Figure 3.

From what is observed in the figure, the rainfall patterns are slightly similar for Chiro and Mieso. Despite the similarities Chiro has higher annual average rainfall of 826 ± 267 mm than that of Mieso (681 ± 193 mm). Of the three, Hirna exhibited the highest annual 30-year average

Figure 4. Averaged-annual rainfalls of Chiro and Mieso

(a)

(b)

Figure 5a,b Analyses of 23 (1991 – 2013) year average start of season (SoS) of Mieso area for the rainfall seasons of (a) February to May and (b) June - September.

rainfall of 929 ± 299 mm. Mieso is the area of interest and thus whenever 30-year data was required, estimation was done from Chiro's data, which is closer and has also

rainfall pattern slightly similar to that Mieso as shown within the dotted ellipses of Figure 4

Table 5a. SoS of Mieso for the rainy season starting from February and lasting until end of May

Dekad	February			March			April			May		
	1	2	3	1	2	3	1	2	3	1	2	3
1991	17	85	1	21	0	26	19	28	11	17	6	25
1992	18	2	0	0	5	10	16	19	69	18	57	7
1993	78	36	4	2	0	0	17	91	29	3	31	12
1994	0	0	0	0	22	34	6	33	12	36	8	6
1995	8	4	0	48	34	16	46	25	34	0	0	26
1996				8	53	198	5	6	24	80	89	80
1997	0	0	0	13	38	51	131	19	7	0	0	8
1998	0	33	2	20	25	17	8	8	11	23	8	3
1999	0	0	3	69	61	2	0	7	4	6	0	12
2000	0	0	0	0	3	5	0	55	30	55	37	37
2001	4	2	0	30	50	35	10	8	6	47	7	26
2002	0	0	0	41	10	9	44	39	0	0	5	0
2003	0	0	4	0	31	6	7	58	99	7	58	99
2004	0	0	0	0	49	26	35	97	20	3	0	0
2005	0	9	0	17	61	19	0	31	61	28	64	7
2006	0	18	8	1	42	17	152	10	15	32	0	6
2007	13	0	6	0	0	17	47	180	4	1	0	12
2008	0	0	0	0	0	0	26	33	0	24	7	7
2009	0	0	3	0	1	29	62	36	19	0	15	0
2010	35	10	26	192	11	76	42	69	52	22	10	0
2011	0	0	0	0	58	0	10	14	12	9	86	23
2012	0	0	0	0	0	7	39	27	30	21	2	9
2013	0	0	0	0	66	62	0	21	90	93	0	14

Table 5b. SoS of Mieso for the rainy season starting from June to September

Dekad	June			July			August			September		
	1	2	3	1	2	3	1	2	3	1	2	3
1991				35	8	17	115	26	58	25	9	32
1992	25	1	10	23	7	12	25	1	10	53	6	12
1993	0	2	3	46	10	22	41	24	35	9	39	23
1994	0	0	10	51	116	81	48	42	0	39	34	41
1995	7	2	10	38	47	9	50	25	28	30	30	0
1996	35	16	29	94	99	55	73	15	81	14	17	43
1997	9	10	23	40	23	41	11	44	71	29	10	0
1998	0	24	8	21	18	79	61	23	13	90	23	50
1999	6	8	20	44	54	61	36	55	55	14	43	16
2000	33	0	23	12	4	0	23	37	81	52	21	47
2001	7	10	50	4	26	165	130	57	93	90	31	4
2002	16	6	6	14	21	39	28	29	49	33	16	4
2003	28	31	51	36	23	51	35	57	94	50	88	22
2004	14	4	20	21	64	51	65	50	21	59	50	10
2005	19	27	30	62	55	77	14	40	42	11	85	12
2006	18	21	14	59	23	65	45	193	38	11	45	6
2007	15	5	22	67	34	64	67	34	64	36	47	34
2008	44	13	2	13	49	42	36	22	95	9	4	1
2009	7	15	26	23	28	15	29	44	36	46	27	1
2010	7	2	64	15	83	93	23	24	51	16	69	7
2011	0	15	6	0	55	44	53	41	37	103	13	88
2012	0	5	46	29	34	78	12	53	92	22	66	16
2013	6	10	27	16	68	104	21	76	53	34	28	8

Start of Season (SoS)

There are a number of reasons for crop failure when it

comes to rainfall. From among the reasons is the delay on SoS. In areas where the rainy season is short (not greater than 3 months) and where irrigation is not an

option, delay in start of season implies moisture stress for crops at later times such as during times of seed setting. Figure 5 indicates 23-year-average February to May and June to September dekadal rainfalls of Mieso area.

In order to qualify as the start of season, the first dekad should have a cumulative rainfall of 25 mm and the two consecutive dekads following this dekad must have rainfalls not less than 20 mm each (Senay *et al.*, 2015). As observed in the figure, the rainfall during all the three dekads of February did not reach 25 mm (dashed line in Figure 5a). The start of season for this lactation for the spring rainfall is during the second dekad of March. This reduces the total number of effective rainfall months for this season to less than three months. Based on this result, the month of February is totally excluded from this rainy season. In the same manner, for the following season (June to September), the start of season was not reached until the first dekad of July. Here again the effective rainy season reduces to less than 3 months. Therefore, the month of June is totally excluded from this season.

For the analysis of the dekadal rainfall, the rainfall within a given dekad is compared with the long-term average rainfall of the same period. It provides useful information on the short-term dryness of the area. Even if the long-term-averaged SoS was during the second dekad of March for the Feb. – May rainfall season and the first dekad of July for the June – September rainy season, it was necessary to include February and June to their respective seasons in order the SoS of each year. Tables 5a and 5b show the number of times each year dekadal value was below the long-term dekadal-averaged values during the two seasons.

Looking at the rainfall patterns of the totals of the first 10 years (only one year each of the decades of 1991 – 2000 and of 2001 – 2010), satisfied the 23-years-averaged SoS of the second dekad of March. The years were 1997 and 2004. During the 23 years short-term drought occurred at the area 91% of the time because of the delay of SoS. Start of season beyond the second dekad of March is considered as failed season since the duration of rainfall falls below 90 days and the farmers have to rely on early maturing crops. Overall, a reasonable season is expected if start of season occurs during the first dekad of March or earlier but this was not observed at this location.

If the rainfall in the month of June shows some improvement over the years, the delay of the start of season could be seen as the slight shift of season. But to check whether this is what has actually happened or not, it is important to see the rainfall pattern of the second season, which starts in June and ends in September (Figure 5b).

In the case of this second season, the 23 year-averaged values indicate the second dekad of July as the appropriate SoS during most years. This is suitable for crops that mature within 90 days. But looking back at the

individual years (Table 2), there is no indication of the shifting of the Feb. – May season even though the first dekad of June had adequate rainfalls in 1992, 1996, 2000, 2003 and 2008.

For the second rainy season start of season did not occur until the first dekad of July. The years 1994, 1996, 1997, 1999, 2003, 2005-2007, 2009 and 2012 had SoS that is similar to the 23-year-averaged SoS. The SoS started earlier than the first dekad of July 22% of the time. Hence, the most probable planting time should be during the first or the second dekad of July, which also agrees with the 23-year-average (Figure 5b). The success rate of crops increases if the onset of season is during the first dekad of July or earlier, but the chance for this to happen is less than 50%.

Overall, considering the two rainy seasons, the years during which both seasons did not experience appropriate onset of season were 1991-1993, 1995, 1998, 2000, 2002, 2008, 2010/2011 and 2013. The simultaneous delay of SoS during those years is assumed to have contributed to the drought that occurred in some of those years.

Dekadal dryness indicator

For this case the full 23 years data of Mieso was used. The 23-year average for the rainy season March to May is shown by the dotted line and the solid line show the 10% reduction from the average. Based on this analysis, anything lower than the solid line (< 207 mm of rain) is considered as a dry year. Accordingly, for this season the numbers 7 – 9 (which correspond to the years 1992 – 1994), 13 and 14 (1998 and 1999), 2002 and 2008 were dry years (Figure 6).

During the following season (July – September) of the same years, 1991-1993, 1995, 1997, 2000, 2002, 2008 and 2009 were dry years. The years during which the two seasons were dry were 1992, 1993, 2002, 2008 and 2009. When the rainfalls of the two seasons simultaneously fail during the same year, the local people have nothing to look for except waiting for relief aid.

Runs theory

Runs theory has the ability to indicate drought with its intensity and duration. The numbers below the threshold generally indicate rainfall deficit but if the deficit is not large or if it does not continue over a couple of years it may not necessarily indicate drought. Figure 7 shows the bar plots of each of the two seasons and for the combination of the two seasons together.

MAM represents the rainy season of March to May. According to the runs theory, except for the year 1998, the remaining 4 years (1986 to 1990) were benign years. Again there were dry years from 1991 to 1995 followed

(a)

(b)

(c)

Figure 6. Study-years-averaged (a) March – May, (b) July –September and (c) the combined seasons rainfalls

(a)

(b)

(c)

Figure 7. RUNS theory bar plot of (a) March to May, (b) July to September and (c) the two seasons combined

by three benign years. From 1999 to 2004 were dry years followed by three benign years. The MAM rainfall deficit has a cycle from 1 year to 3 years. When the dry years are consecutive, the intensity of drought is relatively small but that occurs at the expense of longer duration. This is manifested by values below zero. In general, according to the runs theory the years 1988, 1991 – 1995, 1999 – 2004, 2008 – 2009 and 2011-2012 were all dry years.

JAS represents the months of July, August and September. The three months rainfall in this case shows less drought incidences compared to the MAM rainfall season. The moderate droughts had cycles of 10 years whereas the mild droughts had cycles of five years. The rainfall deficit years were in 1987, 1990, 1992 and 1993, 1995, 1997 and 1998, 2000, 2002 and 2003, 2008 and 2009 and last 2014 (Figure 5b).

Table 6. Summary values of L, D and I of the two seasons shown for the deficit years

Year	L (y)	D (mm)	I (mm/y)
1991-1993	3	-267	-89
1995	1	-9	-9 (very mild)
2000	1	-2	-2 (very mild)
2002-2003	2	-234	-117
2008-2009	2	-215	-107.5

(a)

(b)

(c)

Figure 8. SPI evaluated for the rainy seasons (a) March to May, (b) July to September and (c) for the combined.

Since the area has bimodal rainfall, people have slight chance of recovery when they get JAS rainfall after the failure of MAM rainfall. Hence looking at the combined (i.e. 6-month) rainfall is necessary to look at the years when the people face rainfall deficits in both seasons. For this, both the MAM and JAS rainfalls are plotted together to represent the total rainfalls of the two seasons (Figure 5c).

The stacked bar plots of MAM and JAS shown together indicate the years during which the rainfall failed in both rainy seasons. In areas with bimodal rainfall, failure of rain in both seasons affects the lives of people substantially. The problem is even more severe when it extends beyond one year as observed in this case, during the years 1991-1993, 1999 and 2000, 2002 and 2003 and 2008 and 2009. What is shown for the two seasons is in complete agreement with what was observed on the ground during those years according to the report of West Hararghe Disaster Management Office. The length (L in y), deficit sum (D) and the intensity ($I = D/L$) of the combined two seasons is summarized in Table 6.

As seen in the table, the actual years that could be considered as drought years were: 1991 – 1993, 2002/2003 and 2008/2009. The intensity of drought (whenever it occurred over two consecutive years) was slightly higher than those that occurred during a single year. Intense droughts happened after roughly every ten years and sometimes every five to six years whereas the mild ones occurred every other year or every two years. That explains why the people of the area are continuously in need of relief aid.

Evaluation of drought using SPI

The SPI is considered to be more robust drought indicator than the former three. This is because of its ability to tell the levels of droughts as moderate, severe or extreme (WMO, 2012). Figure 8 shows the 3-month SPIs of the two seasons and 6-month SPI of the combined seasons.

According to Figure 6a, out of the total 30 years (disregarding 2016), 4 or (13%) of the years were drought years. However there was only one extreme (1988), one severe (2008) and two moderate (2002 and 2012) drought years during this season. The rainfall deficits were generally more consecutive than the surplus rainfall years. The remaining years (87%) had near normal or above normal rainfalls. The moderate drought years seem to have a cycle of 10 years.

The July –September season had five drought years (16%). Out of the five, two were severe (1992 and 2001) whereas the remaining three (2002, 2003 and 2015) were moderate drought years.

The combined season gives a better picture of the drought since it indicates the annual pattern. The 6-month SPI shows six (20%) drought years out of which one was severe (1992) and five were moderate (1993, 2002, 2003, 2008 and 2009) drought years. The near normal rainfall years were more dominated by consecutive rainfall deficits.

Choices of probability distributions

The 6-month SPI was calculated using the sum of MAM

Figure 9. Four probability distributions fitted to 6-month data.

(a)

(b)

Figure 10. 6-month SPI evaluated using (a) generalized extreme value and (b) gamma distributions fittings

Figure 11. Loglogistic distribution fitted to D_i data points

and JAS rainfalls together. The two seasons follow each other with only one month apart, which generally has very small rainfall. Looking at the two seasons together shows whether the two seasons failed simultaneously during the same year or not. It indicates the severity of the problem when the two fail together. The four probability distributions fitted to the data are shown in Figure 9.

From among the four distributions, the generalized extreme value (Gev) and the gamma functions showed better fits and therefore the SPIs were evaluated using the two functions to compare differences among the probability distributions selected. Figure 10 shows the SPIs obtained by the two different fits (Gev and gamma functions).

Looking at both figures, because of the similarities of the fits of the two distribution functions, the results are also very identical. Severe drought years occurred in 1992 and 2002. Then 6 years later there was close to severe drought in 2008. Thus the cycles are 10 years for the severe and 6 years for the close to severe droughts. Moderate droughts occurred in 1993, 2001, 2003 and 2009. The moderate droughts occurred either before or after the severe droughts (1993) and sometimes even before and after (e.g. 2001 and 2003). It is expected that such droughts occurred every 10 years and the moderate ones, after six years. The out of normal rainfalls had nearly the same frequencies for the wet (6) and drought (7) years. Thus it is safe to say that the area has 20% drought years, 20% years of relatively surplus rainfall while the remaining years (about 60%) were close to normal.

Based on the 6-month SPI, extreme wet (1996) and severe drought (1992) occurred once every thirty or more years. The year 2006 was a wet year (note we have excluded the 31th year or 2016 from the analysis), which means a cycle of ten years if 2016 is considered. Similarly one can assume the same cycle between 1992

and 2002 drought years. The moderately wet and the moderate droughts had cycles ranging from four to six years. The moderate droughts, whenever they occurred, lasted two consecutive years. Hence from the 6-month SPI, the bad years were 1992/1993, 2002/2003 and 2008/2009.

Standardized Precipitation and Evapotranspiration Index (SPEI)

The SPEI was calculated in the same manner as SPI (i.e., for the 6-month). In order to calculate the potential evapotranspiration only temperature was considered since the data of the other parameters were missing to use the Penman-Monteith (PM) method. Besides, the SPEI was calculated for the years 1991 – 2013 due to the missing data. Computations of rainfall and temperature from Chiro's data were not done since two estimations increase the error. The distribution that was used to fit into the sum D_i data is shown in Figure 11.

The loglogistic was amenable and fitted the data points very well. The cumulative density function (cdf) values were calculated using the loglogistic probability distribution parameters. Both were carried out using Matlab software. Finally, the SPEI values were computed using Eq. (2.7 and 2.8). The SPEI values of 6-month of all the years is shown in Figure 12.

According to the SPEI, the years 2002 and 2008 were the extremely and severely dry years, respectively. The years 1992 and 2009 were moderately dry years. 2003 was a mild dry year. On the other hand, during the same period there were only two moderately wet years (1996 and 2006) and five slightly wet years (2001, 2005, 2007, 2010 and 2013). With the SPEI analysis the drought cycles were roughly 6 – 10 years.

The results of the five types of drought indicators are

Figure 12. SPEI calculated for 6-month(combinations of two rainy seasons) using 23 year data

Table 7. Summary table of the five drought indices applied on 6-months data

Drought index	Dry/drought years	Remark
Start of season (SoS)	1991, 1992, 2000, 2002	May require end of season
Dekadal dryness indicator	1992, 1993, 2002, 2008 and 2009	-
Runs theory	1992, 1993, 2002, 2008, 2009	-
SPI	1992, 1993, 2002, 2003, 2008 and 2009	
SPEI	1992, 2002, 2003, 2008 and 2009	

summarized in Table 7. The summaries are given for the 6 – month data.

As seen from the summary table, all the indices could clearly capture the drought years fairly well. Start of season should be used with end of season since in some years the rainy season may start well but may fail towards the middle or towards the end of the season. Runs theory may sometimes require some kind of demarcation to show uniformity with the others. When temperature of an area does not fluctuate very much and when the scales of SPEI are defined in the same manner as those of SPI, the two give nearly identical results.

Relating the drought years to ENSO and IOD

Based on the summary Table 3.4, attempts are made to link the drought years with ENSO and IOD events. El Niño and Southern Oscillation (ENSO) are tropical coupled ocean-atmosphere phenomena and they arise due to ocean-atmosphere interactions in the tropical Pacific. The ENSO phenomenon is linked with the variations in atmospheric and ocean conditions or in the climate conditions arising from variations in sea surface temperatures (SST) and atmospheric pressure across the tropical Pacific Ocean. ENSO comprises of two coupled

nature, the El Niño or ocean, and the Southern Oscillation or the atmospheric component (McGregor and Ebi, 2018).

Another mode of coupled ocean-atmosphere interaction over the tropical Indian Ocean is the Indian Ocean Dipole Mode (IOD) (Stuecker *et al.*, 2017). The IOD usually begins to develop in boreal summer, peaks in fall and decays rapidly in winter (Wang and Wang, 2013). The two operate independently but the proximity between the Indian and Pacific Oceans and the existence of oceanic and atmospheric pathways facilitate mutual interactions between these tropical climate modes (Stuecker *et al.*, 2017). According to McGregor and Ebi (2018) there are non-symmetric relationships between ENSO and the IOD.

El Niño events are associated with high sea surface temperatures and they are warm events. Wang and Wang (2013) divide El Niño into two categories; El Niño Modoki I, which is the SST anomalies that originate in the equatorial central Pacific and the El Niño Modoki II, which is associated with subtropical northeastern Pacific. The former is symmetric SST anomaly about the equator and is associated with the positive IOD. The latter is asymmetric distribution and is associated with negative IOD. According to the authors, El Niño Modoki I weakens the Walker Circulation in Indo-Pacific region and reduces

precipitation in the eastern tropical Indian Ocean.

The 1992, 2002, 2003 and 2009 droughts occurred during El Niño years while the 2008 drought occurred during La Niña year, which means drought can occur during both events or even during the transition period. Few years are under the influence of only one specific El Niño phase while most years are characterized by a transition phase (Wang and Wang, 2013). El Niño Modoki I events occurred in 1991 with IOD of 0.7, in 1997 with IOD of 3.2 and in 2002 with IOD of 1.3 (Wang and Wang, 2013). Out of the three, the 2002 was the extreme drought year. Positive combined El Niño and southern oscillations occurred during 1990 – 1995 whereas the negative occurred during 1996 and 1997. During the positive ENSO years there is probability of dryness while during the negative years wet seasons are possible. In the past El Niño has affected crop seasons in Ethiopia. Cases in point were the first crop season of 1987 and the 1991/92 El Niño that lasted 14 months. It also affected second crop season of 1991 (Rojas *et al.*, 2014).

There are cycles where consecutive years were under the influence of a warm or a cold phase. Eight of the years from 1993 to 2000 were under the influence of La Niña. From 2001 to 2007 were years under the influence of El Niño and the years 2008 to 2013 were influenced by the La Niña effect. Neutral and La Niña years during the dominance of El Niño behave as El Niño years, causing extended droughts in agriculture. On the other hand, an El Niño year that takes place during La Niña's dominance seems to have less impact on crop areas (Rojas *et al.*, 2014). This could explain why El Niño of 1997/98 did not produce the impacts anticipated since the El Niño occurred during the La Niña dominance. On the other hand, the extreme drought of 2002 occurred during El Niño year and also during the El Niño dominance. The 2008 drought seems to be due to the positive ENSO.

El Niño 1997/98 was classified as strong in intensity. It started in April-May-June 1997 and lasted 12 months (Rojas *et al.*, 2014). However, its impact on agriculture was not directly correlated with the intensity of the phenomenon though some spots of moderate drought were recorded for instance, in countries like Niger, the Sudan, Ethiopia and northern Tanzania (Rojas *et al.*, 2014).

There was moderate intensity El Niño in 2002/03 that peaked in October-November-December 2002. It began in April-May-June 2002 and lasted ten months (Rojas *et al.*, 2014). The conditions prior to El Niño 2002/03 were considered neutral. This El Niño affected the first crop season in 2002 and the drought affected among other African countries, the Sudan, Ethiopia and coast Province in Kenya. It also affected second crop season of 2002 and as a result drought affected some spots in Ethiopia. This El Niño must have been the major cause of the extreme drought observed in Mieso area during this year. In 2003 the first crop season was affected and drought affected Ethiopia, Nigeria, Tanzania, Botswana

(severely affected) and South Africa (Rojas *et al.*, 2014).

El Niño of 2009/10 was classified as moderate in intensity and peaked in November-December-January 2009. It began relatively late in June-July-August 2009 and lasted ten months. During the first crop season of 2009, the impacts of El Niño on agriculture were noted in several countries. In Africa countries affected were Sierra Leone, the Sudan with moderate drought, while Ethiopia, Somalia and Kenya experienced one of the worst droughts in 30 years (Rojas *et al.*, 2014). During the second crop season of 2009, the countries affected in Africa were Somalia (some moderate drought spots), Kenya and Tanzania.

IOD is a powerful modulator of Indian Ocean climate during its positive phase. During its negative phase, IOD drives Indian Ocean climate in the opposite direction, rendering wetter than normal conditions at the equatorial eastern Indian Ocean (Hameed *et al.*, 2018). The mechanisms that generate and sustain IOD lie entirely within the equatorial Indian Ocean, just as ENSO's genesis mechanisms lay entirely within the Pacific basin. The two influence each other because of the physical proximity between the Indian and Pacific basins and the existence of oceanic (Wijffels and Meyers, 2004) and atmospheric pathways (Hameed *et al.*, 2018)

The problem of IOD–ENSO interaction is interesting due to the significant correlation that exists between the time series of IOD and ENSO during the boreal fall season. Co-occurrences of El Niño with positive IOD and La Niña with negative IOD, account partly for the large correlation. However, external factors, such as the global warming trend, decadal variations and the ENSO-induced basin-wide SST anomaly, introduce a spurious zonal SST gradient in the Indian Ocean SST (Saji and Yamagata, 2003b). The positive IOD event of 1997 co-occurred with El Niño events, while the negative IOD event of 1996 and 2013 co-occurred with La Niña events (Hameed *et al.*, 2018). Strong IOD events occur during strong (1997) and weak (1994 and 2006) El Niño events.

Negative IOD brings higher than normal rainfall over equatorial East Africa (Behera *et al.*, 2005; Saji and Yamagata, 2003a). The effect of IOD on rainfall anomalies are strongest between 10°S and 10°N, and extend from the Indian Ocean coast until about 25°E (Hameed *et al.*, 2018).

The reason that ENSO appears to be associated with rainfall anomalies over equatorial East Africa is due to the co-occurrence of IOD and ENSO events. But it is likely a consequence of IOD–ENSO interaction (Ashok *et al.*, 2001, 2004): when a positive IOD co-occurs with an El Niño, the IOD-induced enhancement of monsoon rainfall is countered by the suppression of the same rainfall by El Niño's atmospheric teleconnections. (Hameed *et al.*, 2018)

CONCLUSION

Mieso district is one of the areas of Western Haraghe that is persistently affected by drought though the area is well known for its sorghum production. In this study, 23-year meteorological data of the district was used and when necessary, the 7-year data were estimated from the nearby (30 km) meteorological station (Asebe Teferi also known by the name Chiro) to check the frequency and intensity of droughts. For this purpose, five drought indicators were used. They were; start of season, dekadal drought indicator, runs theory, standard precipitation index (SPI) and the standard precipitation and evapotranspiration index (SPEI).

The area has bimodal rainfall but both seasons have growing days of slightly less than 3 months as observed from dekadal rainfall patterns. From the start of season analysis the planting dates for the March – May season was found to be the second dekad of March and for the July to September season, the first dekad of July.

The entire drought indicators captured the dry years very well, but the use of multiple drought indicators is necessary to know the intensities of droughts. The SPI and SPEI gave nearly identical results.

The conclusion that can be drawn is that the rainfall of the area is not adequate to overcome evapotranspiration during some years and there were more severe dry years than severely wet years. The severe dry years have cycles of six and ten years as moderately wet years. The extreme drought of 2002 may have cycles of 30 years or more. As far as SoS is concerned, strict planting dates have to be followed to avoid yield losses. The drought of the area appears to be related to ENSO and positive IOD years.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This study was financed by the Research Office of Haramaya University. The meteorological data was obtained from the Ethiopian Meteorological Agency.

REFERENCES

- Anderson B, Strahler AH (2008). Visualizing weather and climate. Wiley Global Education.
- Ashok K, Guan Z, Saj NH, Yamagata T (2004). Individual and combined influences of ENSO and the Indian Ocean Dipole on the Indian summer monsoon. *J. Climate*, 17(16), 3141–3155.
- Ashok K, Guan Z, Yamagata T (2001). Impact of the Indian Ocean Dipole on the relationship between the Indian monsoon rainfall and ENSO. *Geophysical Research Letters*, 28(23), 4499–4502.
- Bae, Seungjong, Sang-Hyun Lee, Seung-Hwan Yoo and Taegon Kim (2018). Analysis of Drought Intensity and Trends Using the Modified SPEI in South Korea from 1981 to 2010. *Water* 10, 327
- Behera SK, Luo JJ, Masson S, Delecluse P, Gualdi S, Navarra A (2005). Paramount impact of the Indian Ocean Dipole on the East African short rains: A CGCM study. *J. Climate*, 18(21), 4514–4530.
- Blain GC, Meschiatti MC (2015). Inadequacy of the gamma distribution to calculate the Standardized Precipitation Index. *R. Bras. Eng. Agric. Ambiental*, v.19, n.12, p.1129–1135, ISSN 1807-1929
- Hameed SN, Jin D, Thilakan V (2018). A model for super El Niños. *Nature Communications*, 9(1), 2528.
- Hussein K (2007). Characterization of milk production system and opportunity for market orientation: A case study of Mieso District, Oromiya region, Ethiopia. MSc Thesis. Haramaya University.
- Kahsay B (2006). Improving Productivity and Market Success of Ethiopian Farmers: Pilot Learning Wereda: Mieso. Environmental Assessment and Screening Report.
- Kumar MN, CS Murthyb, MVR Sessa Saib, PS Royb, (not dated). On the use of Standardized Precipitation Index (SPI) for drought intensity assessment. National Remote Sensing Centre, Hyderabad, India
- Manatsa D, Behera S (2013). On the epochal strengthening in the relationship between rainfall of East Africa and IOD. *J. Climate* 26(15).
- McGregor GR, Ebi K (2018). El Niño Southern Oscillation (ENSO) and Health: An Overview for Climate and Health Researchers. *Atmosphere* 9(7), 282; doi: 10.3390/atmos9070282
- Paulo AA, Pereira LS (2006). Drought Concepts and Characterization: Comparing Drought Indices Applied at Local and Regional Scales. *Water International*, Volume 31, Number 1, 37–49
- Rojas O, Li Y, Cuman R (2014). Understanding the drought impact of El Niño on the global agricultural areas: An assessment using FAO's Agricultural Stress Index (ASI).
- Saji NH, Yamagata T (2003a). Possible impacts of Indian Ocean Dipole Mode events on global climate. *Climate Research*, 25(2), 151–169.
- Saji NH, Yamagata T (2003b). Structure of SST and surface wind variability during Indian Ocean Dipole Mode events: COADS observations. *J. Climate*, 16(16), 2735–2751.
- Senay GB, NM Velpuri, S. Bohms, M. Budde, C Young (2015). Drought Monitoring and Assessment: Remote Sensing and Modeling Approaches for the Famine Early Warning Systems Network, University of Nebraska – Lincoln Digital Commons@University of Nebraska – Lincoln USGS Staff -- Published Research US Geological Survey
- Stuecker MF, Timmermann A, Jin F, Chikamoto Y, Zhang W, Wittenberg AT, Widiastih E, Zhao S (2017). Revisiting ENSO/Indian Ocean Dipole phase relationships. *Geophysical Research Letters*. <https://doi.org/10.1002/2016GL072308>
- Wang X, Wang C (2013). Different Impacts of Various El Niño Events on the Indian Ocean Dipole. *Climate Dynamics*
- Wijffels SE, Meyers GM (2004). An intersection of oceanic wave guides: Variability in the Indonesian throughflow region. *J. Phy. Oceanography*, 34, 1232–1253.
- WMO (2012). Standardized Precipitation Index User Guide. World Meteorological Organization, WMO-No. 1090
- Wu H, Svoboda MD, Hayes MJ, Wilhite DA, Wen F (2007). Appropriate application of the Standardized Precipitation Index in arid locations and dry seasons. *Int. J. Climatol.* v.27, p.65-79., <http://dx.doi.org/10.1002/>
- Zargar A, R. Sadiq, B. Naser, F.I. Khan (2011). A review of drought indices. *Environ. Rev.* 19: 333–349.